

Construction of a Geometry In Relativity

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I - FOREWORD

This study is halfway between mathematics and physics. It is not a question of pondering on physics in theory of relativity. This physics is perfectly known and has been verified for more than one century. We respect it completely. It is not a question either to build a new mathematical theory but only to use mathematical tools, also perfectly known, to try a less analytical and more geometrical approach : the analytic calculus, largely used in geometry of Relativity, makes it possible to obtain often difficult numerical results of interpretation in geometry.

What we want to demonstrate is that, on the one hand, the geometry in Relativity can be tackled with a completely geometrical approach, with a completely geometrical representation allowing to break away from tensorial calculus in accelerated reference frames, with a part of strongly reduced analytic calculus and, on the other hand, that the structure of space is more complex than the perception we have in the Euclidean reference frame. The structure of the space is double.

This geometry is particular in the fact that the defined norm in an Euclidean reference frame is unstable : it varies during a change of reference frame if the two reference frames are in relative movement. It results in more important geometrical difficulties if the moving reference frame is accelerated. Existing isomorphism between space, considered as vector space, and its dual containing the laws of mechanics regarded as linear forms, is broken. To restore this isomorphism, it is necessary to transform dual in the same way as the vector space, i.e. to build a base of dual and use tensorial calculus. This mathematical range is very heavy.

II- PRESENTATION OF THIS APPROACH

The geometrical difficulties, related to the rupture of the Euclidian norm during a change of reference frame, are connected to the physical phenomenon, perfectly known and verified, of invariance speed of light. If this particular physical phenomenon did not exist, there would be no rupture of the Euclidian norm in a change of reference frame. The laws of transformation allowing to pass from the fixed reference frame in the mobile reference frame would result in a simple translation (affine transform of ratio 1) and/or in a rotation which only changes the axes. The mechanics would be very close to the classic mechanics, the only consisting difference, during a change of reference frame, would be in an affine transform of the expression of the time (translation) of the form :

$$t' = t - \frac{vx}{c^2}$$

with t' = time in the moving reference frame, t = time in the fixed reference frame, v = relative speed of the moving reference frame,

x = abscissa of the point

The phenomenon of invariance of the light speed is mathematically translated by the radical

$$\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \text{ which breaks the Euclidian norm.}$$

In our geometrical approach, we have wanted to transform this analytic expression by a trigonometric expression. The idea is not entirely new because the theoretical development of MINKOWSKI bases on a similar approach. But MINKOWSKI uses the hyperbolic

trigonometry. We have used circular trigonometry by the change of variable $\sin \theta = \left| \frac{v}{c} \right|$ with

$$0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}$$

Under these conditions, we have $\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = \cos \theta$ which leads in imagining a particular

rotation of angle θ . With this intention, we have imagined that the space, considered as vector space, is imbedded in a vector space of higher dimension (all this is developed in the following theoretical part) and we built the rotation there. The space appears then as direct sum of two vector subspaces (supplementary vector subspaces).

The first of these vector subspaces is identical to the vector space contained in the fixed reference frame (for this reason, we call it "real" space). It corresponds to what would be the vector space contained in the mobile reference frame if the phenomenon of invariance light speed did not exist. The second vector subspace is directly related to the phenomenon of invariance of light speed. Besides, this vector space is deduced by a linear transformation (product of a rotation by a homothety) from part of "real" space. We call it "supplementary space". The parameters appear there with an opposite sign to the one that they have in the "real" space.

The representation of space appears thus in a completely geometrical form the study of which requires few analytic calculus.

III - RESULTS OBTAINED

We have showed that it is possible to think, in geometry, only in the "real" space and to deduce from it a complete representation of the space : to do so we use the geometrical properties of the "supplementary" space, deduced from the "real" space by the above mentioned linear transformation, then we make a vector space summation.

We have showed that the same process of geometrical reasoning in the "real" space, then extension by a linear transformation in the "supplementary" space applies also in mechanics, even in accelerated reference frames. It is thus possible to build a complete image of space in accelerated reference frames without constructing a basis of the dual and without using tensorial calculus.

When the trajectory is curved, the calculus becomes heavier because it is necessary to be brought back, at every moment, under the conditions of an axial trajectory by the use of rotations and translations of the fixed reference frame.

We have also calculated the radius of curvature of the space at any time t in axial accelerated reference frames and have defined the center of curvature.

The expression of energy (mass) is related to the choice of the reference frame. Thus, energy is not an intrinsic parameter. Its nature is thus geometrical. We have chosen to give a vector representation of it. It changes nothing else but its representation on a normed oriented axis. Thus, to the mass appearing in a vector form, we apply the same rotation as with the other parameters of space (geometrical space, time). The mass appears invariant then in the “real” space. But its expression, after the same rotation as that of the other parameters of space, is modified by the same homothetic transformation.

Thus, mechanics appearing in the “real” subspace would be identical to the mechanics of NEWTON if the measurement of time were universal, i.e. if the light speed were infinite. The only difference with the mechanics of NEWTON in the “real” subspace would result in this context from the finitude of the light speed.

The not empty supplementary subspace whose existence is associated with the invariance of the light speed, contains physical and geometrical parameters (parameters of geometrical space, of time and of energy). It thus has a physical and geometrical reality, perceived in the moving reference frame and not perceived in the fixed reference frame. It shows that the structure of the space is more complex than the perception which we have of it in the Euclidian reference frame.

This supplementary subspace moreover has properties of symmetry : the parameters appear in with a negative sign. The mass of negative value suggests a negative gravitation. It thus appears in the above mentioned homothety and applied to mechanics.

The phenomenon of invariance of the light speed appears thus as an interaction between the light propagation (propagation of the electromagnetic waves) and a not directly perceived symmetrical space.

IV - GENERAL THEORY

Let us consider, temporarily, a space of dimension 3 and, temporarily also, within the framework of the simple relativity with a frame of reference of LORENTZ.

We thus have two Euclidian reference frames in uniform linear relative movement. One is qualified “fixed” and the other “mobile”.

We now regard the vector space described in these two reference frames as vector subspace of a vector space of higher size, vector space in-which it is imbedded.

We are going to define a particular rotation in this extended space.

A. CONSTRUCTION OF THE NEW REFERENCE FRAME

The 2 reference frames are $R(O, x, y, z)$, « fix » et $R'(O', x', y', z')$, « mobile ».

v represents the speed of translation of R' with regard to R , and $-v$ the relative speed of R with regard to R' , c represents the speed of the light propagation.

Figure 1 : Fixed and mobile reference frames

The equations of transformation of LORENTZ are written:

$$x' = \frac{x - vt}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

$$y' = y$$

$$z' = z$$

$$t' = \frac{t - \frac{vx}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

We are going to complete each of the real spaces E and E' , defined by the reference frames $R(O, x, y, z)$ and $R'(O', x', y', z')$ by a supplementary space. Supplemented spaces are indicated by E_c et E'_c .

With this intention, we use the properties of vector space of Euclidean space.

We extend them to supplemented space :

$$\begin{aligned} R(O, x, y, z) &\mapsto Rc(O, x, y, z, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}) \\ R'(O', x', y', z') &\mapsto R'c(O', x', y', z', \bar{x}', \bar{y}', \bar{z}') \end{aligned}$$

We have the scalar product in the Euclidian space. It is a symmetric bilinear form, that can be defined in a vector space of any dimension.

Its quadratic form allows to define the orthogonality, the norm and the distance :

Let us extend the scalar product to E_c and E'_c .

Given V_1 and V_2 two unspecified vectors of E_c and E'_c . The condition of orthogonality results in:

$$V_1 \perp V_2 \Leftrightarrow V_1 * V_2 = 0$$

The norm results from the quadratic form :

$$\|V\| = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^6 x_i^2} \quad (i = 1, 6);$$

$$\text{In addition : } \|V\| = 0 \Leftrightarrow V = 0 \quad (V = \text{isotropic vector})$$

We can define the angle of 2 nonnull vectors from the scalar product :

Given V_1 and V_2 two nonnull vectors, belonging both either to E_c or to E'_c , the angle θ between these 2 vectors is defined by :

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{V_1 * V_2}{\|V_1\| * \|V_2\|}$$

We thus suppose the 6 axes of each reference frame $Rc(O, x, y, z, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$ and

$R'c(O', x', y', z', \bar{x}', \bar{y}', \bar{z}')$ orthogonal and having a norm within the meaning of the scalar product, which makes it possible to define unit vectors on each axis.

The reference frames Rc and $R'c$ thus form each one an orthonormal basis, in E_c and E'_c respectively.

We call E_r and E'_r the restrictions of E_c and E'_c respectively in the “real” space (formerly E and E'), E_v and E'_v , the restrictions of E_c and E'_c in the “supplementary” space. E_r , E'_r , E_v and E'_v thus constitute vector subspaces of E_c and E'_c . Their sums constitute E_c and E'_c .

$$E_c = E_r + E_v \quad ; \quad E'_c = E'_r + E'_v$$

The basis $Rc, R'c, R_r, R'_r, R_v, R'_v$ of $E_c, E'_c, E_r, E'_r, E_v, E'_v$ respectively constitute the basis of corresponding vector spaces and subspaces.

Rotation of axis :

We will superimpose a reference frame $R''c$ with the reference frame $R'c$, in order to define a rotation in space E'_c . The reference frame $R''c$ is identical to the reference frame $R'c$. Its O'' origin coincides with O' .

It is provided with axis $O''x'', O''y'', O''z'', O''\bar{x}'', O''\bar{y}'', O''\bar{z}''$, and with the same norm as $R'c$.

Figure 2 : Juxtaposed reference frames

The coordinates of any point P of E'c are :

$$(x', y', z', \bar{x}', \bar{y}', \bar{z}') \text{ in } R'c.$$

They become $(x'', y'', z'', \bar{x}'', \bar{y}'', \bar{z}'')$ in $R''c$:

$$x' = x''; y' = y''; z' = z''; \bar{x}' = \bar{x}''; \bar{y}' = \bar{y}''; \bar{z}' = \bar{z}''$$

We are interested in the expression $\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$

Given $\sin(\theta) = \left| \frac{v}{c} \right|$; $0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}$. We will consider the so chosen limits later on.

We have :
$$\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = \cos(\theta)$$

We make a rotation of angle θ of the reference frame $R''c$ in the plan

$(O''x'', O''\bar{x}'')$. Other coordinates remaining unchanged, we can write the equations of change of reference frame in the plan

$$(O''x'', O''\bar{x}'')$$

Figure 3 : Rotation of the mobile reference frame

The equations which give the rotation are written :

$$\begin{pmatrix} x'' \\ \bar{x}'' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) \\ -\sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x' \\ \bar{x}' \end{pmatrix}$$

With $x'=0$

We have :

$$\begin{aligned} x'' &= x' \cos(\theta) \\ \bar{x}'' &= -x' \sin(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{But, } x' = \frac{x - vt}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} ; \quad \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = \cos(\theta)$$

$$\Rightarrow x' \cos(\theta) = x - vt$$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} x'' = x - vt \\ \bar{x}'' = -(x - vt) \operatorname{tg}(\theta) \end{cases}$$

The coordinates of any point P of the space in R''c are :

$$x'' = x - vt$$

$$y'' = y$$

$$z'' = z$$

$$\bar{x}'' = -(x - vt) \operatorname{tg}(\theta)$$

$$\bar{y}'' = 0$$

$$\bar{z}'' = 0$$

Let's revert to the domain of definition of the angle θ ($0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}$) :

The change of variable was the following :

$$\text{We had put } \sin^2(\theta) = \frac{v^2}{c^2}.$$

$$\text{We have : } \sin(\theta) = \left| \frac{v}{c} \right| \text{ with } \sin(\theta) \geq 0.$$

The definition of θ being $\pm 2k\pi$, we will keep to it the included values between 0 and 2π .

The value $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ is forbidden because $v < c$.

The domain of possible definition of θ is thus $[0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ and/or $[\frac{\pi}{2}, \pi]$

Considering the necessity of a bijection between θ and v , the domain of definition of θ will belong either to the first or to the second of the above domains.

If the second domain is chosen, when $\sin(\theta) \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow \theta \rightarrow \pi$

Thus, and for reasons of continuity, $v \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow \theta \rightarrow \pi$. For $v=0$, the change of variable induces a rotation of π , i.e. an inversion of sense of axis. Now, and considering the initial hypothesis, for $v=0$, the axis of coordinates must be oriented in the same sense (reference frame of LORENTZ).

Thus, the choice of θ in the domain $[\frac{\pi}{2}, \pi]$ must be excluded.

It results :

- that $0 \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}$
- that the values of the parameters in supplementary space thus are well preceded by the minus sign.

B. GEOMETRICAL INTERPRETATION

In $R''r$, after rotation, we have an image of the space which is identical to that of the space in Rr . It only appears a translation of the reference frame (affine transformation) identical to the one who would appear in classic (Newtonian) mechanics.

The strictly "relativist" property, the consequence of the invariance of the light speed in the change of reference frame, is transferred in the supplementary space and projected in the reference frame $R''v$. In this vector sub-space, the parameters of space are inverted (minus sign).

The laws of transformation in this reference frame are the product, for the concerned parameter, of the same affine transformation as in the passage of Rr in $R''r$ by a homothety of $-\text{tg}(\theta)$ ratio and of which center is the origin.

The "purely relativist" homothety (on the \bar{x}'' coordinate), bound to the invariance of the light speed in the change of reference frame, is valid whatever is the speed of the "mobile" reference frame. Its ratio of homothety ($-\text{tg}(\theta)$), depends only on the instantaneous speed of the "mobile" reference frame with regard to the "fixed" reference frame.

C. GEOMETRICAL CONSTRUCTION

Giving a vector of λ modulus (which represents an element of length λ) in the fixed referential frame. This vector is parallel to the axis of movement of the mobile referential frame. The image of this vector in the mobile referential frame is given by the geometrical construction of the figure 4 :

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} t'' = t - \frac{vx}{c^2} \\ \bar{t}'' = -(t - \frac{vx}{c^2})tg(\theta) \end{array} \right.$$

We have an expression of t on the “real” axis which corresponds to an affine transform closely connected (respecting the law of addition of speeds).

On the “supplementary” axis :

The transform of the “time” coordinate takes a similar form to that we had obtained for the coordinate of geometrical space x' . The “real” coordinate in the mobile reference frame (after affine transform) is transferred on the supplementary axis with a coefficient depending on the instantaneous speed of the reference frame ($-tg(\theta)$), and thus with a minus sign. In this subspace, the time varies in opposite sense of its sense of variation on the “real” axis.

This additional component indicates a distortion of time in the mobile reference frame related to the invariance of light speed.

It is just a corrective term. The obtained result representing a negative variation of time in the supplementary space is not inconsistent with the principle of EINSTEIN according to which two events, connected by a cause and effect link in a reference frame, must be connected by a similar bond in another reference frame, i.e. the change of reference frame must prohibit that in a reference frame the effect precedes the cause.

Indeed, the principle stated above applies to the whole space, i.e. before rotation with the vector sum of the two vector subspaces that we built and, in that case, the submission remains true (see the figure 4 in which the parameter λ represents an interval of time). On the other hand, the above submission does not apply to only one of the two subspaces.

VARIATIONS OF TIME IN THE FIXED REFERENCE FRAME AND IN THE REFERENCE FRAME HAVING DONE THE ROTATION :

$$t'' = t - \frac{vx}{c^2}$$

$$\bar{t}'' = -(t - \frac{vx}{c^2})tg(\theta)$$

We are in the same point of fixed abscissa x , at the two successive moments respectively t_1 and t_2 , v being constant.

$$t_2'' - t_1'' = t_2 - t_1; \bar{t}_2'' - \bar{t}_1'' = -(t_2 - t_1)tg(\theta)$$

E. RELATIVIST DYNAMIC :

A particle of mass m_0 at “rest” is animated by a constant speed \vec{u} . We suppose it to move in space out of any gravitational field (restricted Relativity).

Expression of the mass in movement :

$$m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{\|\vec{v}\|^2}{c^2}}}$$

Expression of the moving mass :

The expression of the energy (mass) is connected to the choice of the reference frame. It is thus not an intrinsic parameter but a parameter of space, which leads to envisage a rotation of θ angle similar to the one we

had defined previously for time and geometrical space. We so consider the energy as a vector space with two dimensions, in a reference frame connected to the mass in movement, this one being motionless in the moving reference frame.

Under these conditions, the vector representing the mass is written, before rotation

$$m' = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{m_0}{\cos(\theta)} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

After the rotation we have :

$$m = \begin{bmatrix} m_0 \\ -m_0 \operatorname{tg} \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

The “real” part of the mass appears invariant.

The “supplementary” part appears with a negative value, (which by no means corresponds to antimatter, with the usual signification in the laboratory).

Note: For $\operatorname{tg}(\theta) = 1 \Leftrightarrow \theta = \pi / 4 \Leftrightarrow \sin(\theta) = \sqrt{2} / 2 \Leftrightarrow v = c / \sqrt{2}$ the absolute value of the mass in the “supplementary” space is equal to the absolute value of the mass in “real” space.

F. GEOMETRY OF SPACE :

In our representation, the space appears in the “mobile” reference frame, after rotation, in the form of a direct sum of two vector subspaces made up one by the same vector space as in the “fixed” reference frame, the other by the transform of a vector subspace of this same vector space by a homothety of center the origin and ratio - $\operatorname{tg}(\theta)$.

The reference frame in movement thus contains the same space as the fixed reference frame plus a not empty one “symmetric” space, containing parameters of geometric space, time and energy, i.e. well possessing a physical reality, and supported by linearly independent axis of those of “real” space and fixed reference frame. This shows that the structure of the space is more complex than the perception we have of it in the fixed reference frame, i.e. in the Euclidean reference frame.

G. GRAPHIC CONSTRUCTION OF THIS REPRESENTATION OF SPACE

The mobile reference frame having made a rotation of angle θ , the parameters being supported by the axis of the “supplementary” space result from the corresponding axis by a homothety of ratio $-\text{tg}(\theta)$, i.e. negative. The geometric representation that we are going to give will thus be build by using a rotation of angle $-\theta$.

Let us imagine two observers, the first in the fixed reference frame, the second in the mobile reference frame after rotation. According to the foregoing, the first observer considering a parameter λ (distance between two points on the x-axis, time interval between two events, expression of a mass), the second observer will perceive the same parameter λ on a first axis of coordinates plus its image by homothety of ratio $-\text{tg}(\theta)$ on a second orthogonal axis to the first one, which can be represented on the following diagram :

Figure 5 : Graphic construction of a relativist parameter

The equations of transformation of LORENTZ being valid whatever the speed, if the speed of the mobile reference frame varies on its axis of translation (axial acceleration), the angle of rotation of the mobile reference frame follows the variations speed of the mobile reference frame, which allows us to build an image of geometrical space in the case of an axial acceleration (see figure 6 : Graphic construction of parameters with different speeds).

Figure 6 : Graphic construction of parameters with different speeds

We trace the graph (figure 7) of the function $y = -\text{tg}(\arcsin(x))$ in an orthonormed reference frame of origin O. We choose to represent the speed ($= v$) of the mobile reference frame with regard to the light speed ($= v/c$) by choosing $c = 1$. In that case, x varies between 0 and 1.

For a speed v (with $x = v, c = 1$), we draw in the point of abscissa x a parallel with the y -axis. It cuts the graph of y at the point $M(v, -\text{tg}(\theta))$. From this point M , we draw the parallel line with the x -axis. It cuts the parallel line drawn with the y -axis from the point $(1,0)$ at the point P . By construction, the straight line OP forms an equal angle to $-\theta$ with the x -axis.

After having carried forward the parameter λ on the x -axis, we draw in extremities of the corresponding vector the parallels to the ordinate axis of our reference frame.

The straight line OP intersects these 2 parallels with the ordinate axis by building, as previously, the vector range of λ by the equations of transformation of LORENTZ.

Figure 7 : Complete graphic construction of relativist parameters

We see in this construction that the speed is equivalent to an angle.

This angle (= angle of rotation of the moving reference frame) varies when the reference frame is accelerated, which indicates a bent of space. Let us calculate the corresponding radius of curvature.

H. CURVATURE OF SPACE IN THE CASE OF AXIAL ACCELERATED REFERENCE FRAMES

In the fixed reference frame, the mobile reference frame has a movement of accelerated translation along the X axis of the fixed reference frame.

At the instant t, the origin of the mobile reference frame is at the point O. Given M any point of the axis of translation of the mobile reference frame (= X-axis of the fixed reference frame). M' represents this point after rotation in the mobile reference frame. At this time, the

origin of the mobile reference frame has a speed v and covers the distance $dx = v \cdot dt$ during an infinitesimal interval of time dt .

According to the foregoing, the image ds of this element dx in the mobile reference frame is represented (see figure 7 : “Complete graphic construction of relativist parameters”) by a vector of coordinates:

$$ds \begin{cases} -v \cdot dt \\ \text{tg}(\theta)v \cdot dt \end{cases}$$

At the point M' this differential element ds is on the right OP of which the gradient is $-\text{tg}(\theta)$ (according to the figure 6 : “Complete graphic construction of relativist parameters”)

During the interval of time dt the gradient p of the differential element ds varies of

$$dp = -\frac{d\theta}{\cos^2(\theta)} ;$$

We suppose that the speed has a positive value v . It is always possible with a change of axis.

$$\sin(\theta) = \frac{v}{c} \Rightarrow \cos(\theta) \cdot d\theta = \frac{dv}{c} \Rightarrow d\theta = \frac{dv}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}$$

$$\text{We have thus : } dp = -\frac{dv}{\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}} ; dp = -\frac{c^2 \cdot dv}{(c^2 - v^2)^{3/2}}$$

Thus, during the time interval dt the differential element ds rotates to an angle

$$d\varphi = -\text{Arctg}\left(\frac{c^2 \cdot dv}{(c^2 - v^2)^{3/2}}\right)$$

$$\text{The radius of curvature } R \text{ is defined by: } R = \frac{ds}{d\varphi} \text{ with } ds = \frac{v \cdot dt}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} ; \quad d\varphi < 0 \text{ for}$$

reason of the direction of the concavity of the curvature to the negative values of the X-axis of the reference frame.

Thus :

$$|R| = \frac{v \cdot dt}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \operatorname{Arctg}\left(\frac{c^2 \cdot dv}{(c^2 - v^2)^{3/2}}\right)}$$

$$|R| = \frac{c \cdot v \cdot dt}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2} \operatorname{Arctg}\left(\frac{c^2 \cdot dv}{(c^2 - v^2)^{3/2}}\right)}$$

$dt \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow (ds \rightarrow 0; dv \rightarrow 0; d\varphi \rightarrow 0) \Rightarrow$ the arc tangent is equivalent to the arc

$$|R| = \lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} \frac{c \cdot v \cdot dt}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2} \frac{c^2 \cdot dv}{(c^2 - v^2) \sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}} \Rightarrow |R| = c \frac{v}{\gamma} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)$$

with γ = instantaneous acceleration of the reference frame.

REMARKS

$\gamma = 0 \Rightarrow R = \infty$ (restricted Relativity – conditions of Lorentz)

At any time, the radius of curvature is the same at any point of the X-axis of the reference frame

I. CENTER OF CURVATURE

The center of curvature is over the perpendicular to the right OP at point M' bearing the element ds , oriented to the negative values of the X-axis of the referential frame.

M being a fixed point on the X-axis of the fixed reference frame, the set of the rights OP (O = accelerated moving origin of the mobile reference frame) constitutes the hull of the curve which represents the curvature of the space when t varies.

COMPLETE REPRESENTATION OF SPACE IN THE CASE OF ACCELERATED REFERENCE FRAMES :

In order to describe not only space but also the movement in the change of reference frame, it is necessary in the same way to transform the laws of mechanics as the vector space was transformed. The laws of mechanics (differential equations) being linear forms and thus being elements of the dual of the vector space, it is necessary to transform the dual in the same way as the vector space (same rotation and same homothety for the vector of the dual).

It is thus possible to conveniently build a dual base from the vector space base. Then the matrix of transformation is applied simultaneously to each vector of the vector space base and to each corresponding vector of the dual base.

In the representation of the space which we have built, the space is divided into two vector sub-spaces : the real sub-space and the supplementary sub-space.

The real sub-space is the same as the vector space represented in the fixed reference frame. It thus has the same dual one. The laws of the mechanics are thus the same in these two space and vector sub-space.

The supplementary subspace is obtained by the product from a rotation and a homothety from a part of the real subspace. The same transformation must thus be applied to the dual. The rotation does not change the dual.

Concerning the homothety :

After making the rotation and before applying the homothety, the symmetric vector subspace is identical (isomorphic) to a part of the real subspace (corresponding to the axis of translation). The dual of this symmetrical subspace is thus the same as that of the corresponding part of the real subspace.

Thus, if we don't proceed any further, the same laws of mechanics would apply in the supplementary subspace and in the isomorphic part of the real subspace.

Because, we simultaneously apply the homothety to the vectors of the supplementary subspace and to the elements of the dual i.e., concrete terms in our case, to the parameters of movement (speed and acceleration) which are linear applications (that belong the dual) and which were calculated in the corresponding part of the real subspace.

We have thus built a complete description of the space and of the movement in the accelerated mobile reference frame at a given instant.

Finally, the image of the space in the supplementary subspace, including the movement, is obtained from the same homothety of a part of the real subspace and of the corresponding movement in this part of the real subspace.

Thus, the mobile reference frame being accelerated along an axis, in the real subspace of the mobile reference frame which is the same as the vector space contained in the fixed reference frame, the expression of time t' in the mobile reference frame at the instant t of the fixed

reference frame is represented by : $t' = t - \int_0^x \frac{v(x)dx}{c^2}$

The abscissa x' of a point of the space at the instant t is represented by $x' = x - \int_0^t v(t)dt$

It is therefore possible to apply the laws of mechanics at an instant t , during a differential element of time, in the real subspace of the mobile reference frame, laws of mechanics (defining the speed and the acceleration) being the same as in the fixed reference frame.

It is then necessary to apply a homothety to the abscissa of the corresponding point of the real space on the corresponding axis of the supplementary space as well as a homothety of its movement on the same axis.

The usual difficulties of representation of the space in accelerated Euclidean reference frames result from the fact that the structure of the space is more complex than the image we have of it in the Euclidean reference frame.

V - FUNDAMENTAL RESULTS

Important note :

The principle of equivalence of EINSTEIN, according to which a reference frame subjected to a gravitation field is locally (at the place of this reference frame) equivalent with an accelerated reference frame, makes it possible to extend all that was known as previously with the case of presence of a gravitation field.

It is thus possible, according to the method indicated here, to describe space and the movements in space in the presence of a gravitation field without it being necessary to build a basis of the dual nor to call on tensor calculus.

Approach of comprehension of the causes of the invariance of the light speed :

Lorentz transformation equations are the mathematical translation of the speed of light invariance phenomenon. The removal of this invariance invalidates the Lorentz transformation equations and therefore the double structure of space which is the geometric consequence. Likewise, the removal of the double structure of space – with, therefore, conservation of the Euclidian norm in reference frame change - invalidates the Lorentz transformation equations and therefore the speed of light invariance phenomenon. The speed of light invariance is therefore directly linked to this double structure of space.

The second vector subspace has no component in the fixed referential frame. It is therefore not directly perceived in the laboratory or the telescope but only indirectly by the break of the Euclidian norm in the moving Euclidian reference frame.

The 2 vector subspaces are therefore distinct and necessarily nested one in the other. Geometric elements of zero length do not exist in physics (they only exist in mathematics). The space is so pixelated, that is to stay in the form of pixels belonging to the 1st and pixels belonging to the 2nd vector subspace, in the manner of the white squares and the black squares of the chessboard.

The light which is directly perceived, in the 1st vector subspace, remains contained and spreads in the 1st vector subspace (visible light). The light which can be in the 2nd vector subspace remains contained and spreads in the 2nd vector subspace (directly invisible subspace). This movement recalls the moving of the bishop on

the chessboard : there is the white bishop, only moving on the white squares, and never meeting the black bishop, only moving on the black squares.

The invariance of the light speed in the space poses that the transfer time of a photon from a pixel of the vector subspace to an adjacent pixel which it belongs to the same vector subspace is a universal constant independent of the movement of the source.

FINAL NOTE

The attempt of highlighting of a negative gravitation can be considered in zones of low extension outside intense gravitational fields, in particular within not very dense gas clouds (thus subjected to low internal forces of gravity) distant from any massive element.

This kind of gas cloud possesses an internal temperature near to that of the surrounding environment (cosmic microwave background).

A force of negative gravitation within such a gas would involve a dilatation of the gas (with decrease of its temperature) and rarefaction of particles in its heart (shape of the cloud approximatively toric).

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This study is not based on any other recent or ongoing study. Only perfectly known elements of physics and mathematics. For any additional information, please refer to university courses in mathematics and physics at levels 1 and 2.

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